

Paediatrics Corrosive Induced Gastric Outlet Obstruction in Children

Tanya Chaturvedi¹, K N Mishra², Sonam³

¹MD Final Year PG, Department of Paediatrics, Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Darbhanga, Bihar, India

²Professor, Department of Paediatrics, Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Darbhanga, Bihar, India

³MD Final Year PG, Department of Paediatrics, Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Darbhanga, Bihar, India

Received: 25-02-2024 / Revised: 23-03-2024 / Accepted: 25-04-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Sonam

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

This prospective cohort study conducted at Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital over 18 months, from September 2022 to February 2024, examined 30 children with corrosive-induced gastric outlet obstruction to evaluate clinical presentation, treatment outcomes, and long-term follow-up. The study findings indicate a high success rate in symptom resolution, with 76.67% of patients achieving complete recovery post-treatment. Surgical interventions were necessary in 66.67% of cases, reflecting the severity of the obstructions. While effective in most cases, surgical approaches were associated with complications, including anastomotic leaks and wound infections. At the 12-month follow-up, significant improvements were observed in nutritional status (83.3%) and quality of life (80%), though the rehospitalization rate was notable at 20%. These outcomes underscore the importance of timely and effective treatment protocols and highlight the need for comprehensive care that addresses both the physical and psychological aspects of recovery. The study emphasizes the ongoing need for preventive measures to reduce the incidence of corrosive ingestion among children.

Keywords: Pediatric Gastric Outlet Obstruction, Corrosive Ingestion, Surgical Treatment, Long-term Management.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Gastric outlet obstruction (GOO) in children represents a critical and challenging pathology, often requiring urgent medical and surgical intervention. While several causes underlie this condition, corrosive-induced gastric outlet obstruction stands out due to its severe implications and complex management. [1] This obstruction occurs following the ingestion of corrosive substances, such as acids and alkalis, which are unfortunately common household items that children might accidentally consume. [2]

The pathophysiology of corrosive-induced GOO revolves around the ingestion of these substances, leading to severe chemical burns in the esophagus and stomach. [3] The acute phase response includes inflammation and edema, which might initially present as symptoms of acute gastritis or esophagitis. However, the long-term sequelae are more concerning as the healing process can lead to fibrosis and stricture formation, primarily at the pylorus or antrum of the stomach, thus leading to obstruction. [4]

The clinical presentation of corrosive induced GOO in children can vary from vomiting, failure to

thrive, and dehydration to more severe complications such as malnutrition and metabolic derangements. Early diagnosis is crucial and is typically achieved through a combination of clinical history, radiographic findings, and endoscopic evaluation. The management strategies for GOO due to corrosive ingestion require a multidisciplinary approach, involving pediatric gastroenterologists, surgeons, nutritionists, and sometimes even psychological support for the child and family due to the traumatic nature of the ingestion event. [5,6]

Recent advances in management focus on less invasive surgical techniques and improved supportive care, but the prevention of corrosive substance ingestion through better safety measures and public education remains the most effective strategy to combat this serious health issue. This introduction sets the stage for a detailed discussion on the pathogenesis, diagnosis, treatment modalities, and preventive measures of corrosive-induced gastric outlet obstruction in the pediatric population, highlighting the critical need for awareness and timely intervention. [7,8]

Methodology

Study Design: This prospective cohort study at Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital evaluates the clinical presentation, treatment outcomes, and follow-up of 30 children with corrosive-induced gastric outlet obstruction.

Study Population: The study included pediatric patients aged 0-18 years diagnosed with gastric outlet obstruction due to corrosive ingestion. Patients with pre-existing gastrointestinal conditions or prior gastrointestinal surgeries were excluded.

Study Period: The study was conducted over an 18-month period, from September 2022 to February 2024, allowing for the evaluation of both short-term and long-term outcomes.

Data Collection

Data were collected at multiple points during the treatment process:

1. Initial Assessment: Documentation of the corrosive agent type and quantity, and initial symptoms.
2. Diagnostic Evaluation: Radiographic and endoscopic examinations to determine the extent of injury.
3. Treatment Details: Types of medical and surgical interventions provided.
4. Follow-up Assessments: Conducted at 1, 6 and 12-months post-treatment to assess recovery and complications.

Outcome Measures

- Primary Outcomes: Resolution of obstructive symptoms, complication rates (including surgical complications).

- Secondary Outcomes: Changes in nutritional status and quality of life.

Statistical Analysis: Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyze the data, with significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Results

The study involved 30 pediatric patients. The age distribution was as follows: 36.7% were aged 0-5 years, 33.3% were 6-12 years, and 30% were 13-18 years. The gender distribution was 60.00% male and 40.00% female. The types of corrosive ingested were evenly split between acid and alkali (12.50% each). The treatment outcomes revealed a high efficacy in the resolution of symptoms, with 76.67% of patients achieving complete resolution. Surgical intervention was required in 66.67% of the cases. Postoperative complications included anastomotic leaks and wound infections, highlighting the complexity of surgical management.

Follow-up assessments showed significant improvement in nutritional status (83.3%) and quality of life (80%). However, the rehospitalization rate was 20%, indicating ongoing challenges in the long-term management of these patients. These results highlight the critical need for effective medical and surgical treatments and underscore the importance of comprehensive postoperative care to improve long-term outcomes in children with corrosive-induced gastric outlet obstruction.

Table 1: Demographic and clinical characteristics

Characteristic	Total Patients (n=30)
Age (years)	
0-5	11 (36.7%)
6-12	10 (33.3%)
13-18	9(30.0%)
Gender	
Male	18(60.0%)
Female	12(40.0%)
Type of corrosive	
Acid	15(50.0%)
Alkali	15(50.0%)
Time of presentation	
<24 hours	8(26.67%)
24-72 hours	12(40.0%)
>72 hours	10(33.33%)

Table 2: Treatment Outcomes

Outcome	Number of Patients	Percentage
Resolution of symptoms		
Complete	23	76.6%
Partial	5	16.7%
None	2	6.7%
Surgical intervention required		
Yes	20	66.7%
No	10	33.3%
Post-operative complications		
Anastomotic leak	2	6.7%
Wound Infection	1	3.3%
Recurrent Obstruction(within 1yr)	2	6.7%

Table 3: Follow-up Outcomes at 12 months

Outcome	Number of Patients	Percentage
Nutritional status improved	25	83.3%
Quality of life improved	24	80.0%
Rehospitalization	6	20.0%

Discussion

The results of this study at Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital (DMCH) shed significant light on the complex management and outcomes of pediatric patients suffering from corrosive-induced gastric outlet obstruction. [9,10] With 76.6% of the participants achieving complete resolution of symptoms post-treatment, the efficacy of the current treatment protocols is evident. However, the need for surgical intervention in two-thirds of the cases highlights the severity of damage that corrosive substances can inflict on the pediatric gastrointestinal tract. [11]

The high rate of surgical intervention (66.7%) in this cohort indicates a predominance of severe cases that could not be managed by medical therapy alone. This aligns with literature suggesting that surgical treatment is often inevitable for corrosive injuries leading to strictures and obstructions, particularly when fibrosis sets in, preventing non-surgical resolution (Xu et al., 2019). Despite the complexity of these procedures, the relatively low complication rate (6.7% experiencing anastomotic leaks or 3.3% wound infections) is encouraging. [12] It reflects advances in surgical techniques and perioperative care, underscoring the importance of specialized pediatric surgical expertise in managing these challenging cases. [13]

The recurrence rate of obstruction within one year in 6.7% of the patients points to the chronic nature of the injury caused by corrosive substances. [14] This finding suggests the necessity for a long-term follow-up strategy that includes not just surgical intervention but also continuous monitoring and possibly repeated interventions, as discussed by

Park et al. (2021). [15] The management of these patients must therefore be holistic and multidisciplinary, involving surgeons, pediatric gastroenterologists, dietitians, and psychological services to address the full range of physical and emotional impacts. [16]

Improvement in nutritional status and quality of life in 83.3% and 80% of patients, respectively, highlights the effectiveness of the comprehensive care these patients received. However, the persistent rehospitalization rate of 20% signals ongoing challenges. This may be partly attributed to complications or recurrences, as well as the psychological and social impacts of the initial corrosive ingestion event, which can complicate recovery trajectories (Smith et al., 2020). [17]

The persistent incidence of corrosive ingestions necessitates stronger preventive measures. Public education about the dangers of household corrosives and secure storage guidelines are critical. Moreover, legislation to restrict the availability of such dangerous substances could further reduce these incidents, as suggested by global trends in countries that have implemented such measures (Jain et al., 2018). [18] This study contributes valuable insights into the clinical management of corrosive-induced gastric outlet obstruction in children, emphasizing the need for prompt, effective treatment and vigilant long-term follow-up. While surgical techniques continue to improve, holistic care encompassing nutritional, psychological, and social support remains crucial to improving outcomes. Lastly, a renewed focus on preventive measures could potentially reduce the incidence of such devastating injuries among children. [19]

Conclusion

This study conducted at Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital provides critical insights into the management of corrosive-induced gastric outlet obstruction in children, emphasizing the effectiveness of current surgical interventions and comprehensive post-operative care. Despite a high success rate in symptom resolution, the necessity for surgical intervention in the majority of cases highlights the severity of this condition. The recurrence of symptoms in some patients underscores the need for ongoing monitoring and possibly iterative treatments. Improvement in nutritional status and quality of life for the majority of patients reflects the success of multidisciplinary management approaches, although the significant rehospitalization rate points to the need for continuous improvement in care strategies. Prevention remains paramount, with enhanced public education and stricter regulations on corrosive substances needed to reduce the incidence of these severe injuries. This study underlines the importance of both acute and long-term management strategies in pediatric patients suffering from this serious condition.

References

1. Smith JD, Brown HA. Gastric outlet obstruction in children: a review of clinical outcomes. *J Pediatr Surg.* 2021;56(2):345-50.
2. Johnson LR, Miller M. Pathophysiology and management of corrosive ingestions in children. *J Pediatr Gastroenterol Nutr.* 2020;70 (3) :391-8.
3. Patel A, Lee S. Surgical approaches to gastric outlet obstruction in pediatric populations. *Surg Clin North Am.* 2022;102(1):123-37.
4. Evans K, Roberts A. Outcomes of conservative versus surgical treatment for corrosive esophageal injuries in children. *Arch Dis Child.* 2019 ;104(10):960-5.
5. Gupta P, Tewari V, Kumar V. Long-term complications following corrosive ingestion in children: a 5-year review. *Indian J Gastroenterol.* 2023;42(1):18-24.
6. Zhou Y, Zhang H, Liu J. Epidemiology and prevention of caustic ingestion in children. *Pediatr Emerg Care.* 2022;38(5):e1073-e1078.
7. Chang MW, Chao HC, Kong MS. Endoscopic findings and management of gastric outlet obstruction in infants and children. *Endoscopy.* 2020;52(3):202-8.
8. Brown S, Johnson K. Nutritional management strategies in children with corrosive strictures. *Nutr Clin Pract.* 2021;36(4):679-88.
9. Watson L, Bates S. Psychological impact of corrosive injuries in children and their families: A prospective study. *Child Care Health Dev.* 2021;47(1):122-9.
10. Patel R, Chopra A. Radiographic imaging techniques in the diagnosis of gastric outlet obstruction in pediatric patients. *Pediatr Radiol.* 2021;51(8):1375-82.
11. Lee SJ, Park KH. A review of surgical and non-surgical treatments of corrosive injuries in the pediatric stomach. *Int J Pediatr Otorhinolaryngol.* 2020; 131:109843.
12. Kim JH, Moon JS. Follow-up strategies after corrosive injury in children: When and how? *World J Gastroenterol.* 2020;26(22):3061-71.
13. Sanders JE, Hawley P, Levy J. Legislative and preventive measures to combat corrosive ingestions in children: a comparative study. *J Public Health Policy.* 2021;42(2):258-74.
14. Thompson A, Roberts G. Surgical complications and their management in children with corrosive-induced gastric outlet obstruction. *J Surg Res.* 2022; 260:204-12.
15. Davidson T, Newman L. Quality of life assessments in pediatric patients after corrosive injury management. *J Pediatr Psychol.* 2022;47 (5):527-35.
16. Xu, D., et al. (2019). Surgical management of gastric outlet obstruction. *Pediatric Surgery International*, 35(2), 207-214.
17. Park, J., et al. (2021). Long-term outcomes after surgical treatment of corrosive esophageal strictures in children. *Journal of Pediatric Gastroenterology and Nutrition*, 72(3), 399-404.
18. Smith, J., et al. (2020). Psychological impact of pediatric corrosive ingestion. *Child: Care, Health and Development*, 46(5), 589-595.
19. Jain, A., et al. (2018). Preventing corrosive injuries: the need for stricter regulation on household chemicals. *Pediatric Health, Medicine and Therapeutics*, 9, 123-129.